

CHILDHOOD EMOTIONAL ABUSE, RESILIENCE, & RISKY BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG ADULTS: A STUDY OF MALADAPTIVE COPING & PROACTIVE FACTORS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17894009>

Received	Accepted	Published
11 October 2025	21 November 2025	11 December 2025

ABSTRACT

This study examined the associations among childhood emotional abuse, resilience, and risky behaviour in a university-based sample of young adults. A total of 210 participants aged 18–25 years (69.52% female, 30.47% male) were recruited using purposive sampling. Standardized instruments—the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ), Brief Resilience Scale (BRS), Stimulating and Instrumental Risk Questionnaire (S&IRQ), and the Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale (DOSPERT)—were administered to assess the study variables. Findings revealed that emotional abuse was significantly associated with increased engagement in risky behaviours, indicating that individuals exposed to higher levels of emotional maltreatment during childhood were more likely to exhibit maladaptive behavioural patterns in young adulthood. In contrast, resilience showed a significant negative association with emotional abuse, suggesting that emotionally maltreated individuals tend to demonstrate reduced capacity to recover and adapt to stress. Regression analysis further demonstrated that emotional abuse and resilience together significantly predicted risky behaviour outcomes, with emotional abuse emerging as a meaningful predictor of increased risk-taking tendencies. Gender comparisons showed that male participants scored higher on risky behaviours, whereas no meaningful gender differences were observed for emotional abuse or resilience. Overall, the results highlight the persistent effects of childhood emotional abuse on later behavioural and psychological functioning, emphasizing its role in diminishing resilience and increasing vulnerability to risky behaviours.

Keywords: Childhood Emotional Abuse, Resilience, Risky Behaviour, Stimulating Risk, Instrumental Risk.

INTRODUCTION

Experiencing childhood trauma has profound and long-lasting consequences that extend across developmental stages, impairing emotional and psychological functioning both in childhood and adulthood. The present study focuses specifically on childhood emotional abuse and its role in shaping later outcomes among young adults. Emotional abuse during childhood has been strongly linked to difficulties in emotion regulation, heightened vulnerability to maladaptive coping patterns, and increased likelihood of engaging in risky behaviours in later life. Such

adverse early experiences may also weaken an individual's capacity to adapt positively to stress, leading to diminished resilience (Dasgupta et al., 2017). Repeated exposure to emotional stress has been shown to disrupt neural and psychological development, increasing susceptibility to long-term adjustment problems.

Resilience, understood as the ability to recover, adapt, and maintain functioning despite adversity, plays a central role in moderating the effects of emotional abuse. However, young adults who have experienced chronic emotional maltreatment often

exhibit reduced resilience, making them more vulnerable to risk-taking tendencies and emotional instability. Therefore, the present study examines how childhood emotional abuse influences resilience and contributes to engagement in risky behaviours, highlighting the lasting effects of early emotional maltreatment on later developmental outcomes (Baker et al., 2018).

Risk-taking behaviour refers to the tendency to engage in actions that may pose physical, emotional, or psychological harm, such as alcohol misuse, binge drinking, substance use, unsafe driving, and unprotected sexual activity. This includes the domains of social decision-making and health and safety behaviours and considers how such tendencies are shaped by traumatic childhood experiences. Augsburger & Elbert argue that individuals who have encountered traumatic events are significantly more likely to engage in risk-taking behaviours (Augsburger & Elbert, 2017).

Childhood Emotional Abuse

Abuse is an emotional reaction to highly distressing events such as accidents, rape, or natural disasters. Initial responses commonly include shock and denial, while long-term effects may involve emotional instability, flashbacks, strained relationships, and physical symptoms such as headaches or nausea (Pearce et al., 2019). Childhood abuse refers to any harmful event experienced during a child's formative years that compromises physical, emotional, or psychological well-being. Traumatic experiences may result from acute incidents such as vehicle accidents, natural disasters, physical or sexual abuse, sex trafficking, or toxic caregiving environments. However, chronic exposure to maltreatment—such as name-calling, humiliation, rejection, emotional withholding, or threats—can also generate significant trauma. The long-term impact of childhood abuse extends into adulthood and significantly contributes to mental health challenges (American Psychological Association, 2021).

In the current study focus was on the childhood emotional abuse. It refers to patterns of degrading, shaming, rejecting, mocking, or isolating a child. These behaviors significantly undermine emotional and psychological development and can produce lasting mental health consequences (Gama et al., 2021).

Effects of Childhood Emotional Abuse

Childhood trauma produces enduring emotional, psychological, and physiological effects. It increases the risk of mental health issues such as substance abuse, reduced resilience, or engagement in risky behaviors. Trauma can impair cognitive functioning—including attention, memory, and executive functioning (Reed et al., 2019)—and disrupt the formation of healthy interpersonal relationships. Trauma also elevates emotional dysregulation, impulsivity, and anger management problems, and has been linked to increased physical health complications (Humphreys et al., 2020).

Resilience

Psychological resilience refers to the capacity to adapt to stress, abuse, or adversity. It is not innate but consists of skills that can be strengthened. Resilient individuals demonstrate emotional regulation, problem-solving, communication skills, and social competence (Sapienza & Masten, 2018; Catherine, 2019; Luthar et al., 2000). Environmental factors such as family cohesion, parental warmth, social support, self-efficacy, and strong values significantly contribute to resilience (Goldstein & Brooks, 2012; Cutter, 2016; Walker, 2020; Hornor, 2017). Resilience is closely linked with effective coping strategies and task-focused coping mechanisms (Folke, 2016).

Risky Behaviours

Risk-taking behavior involves actions with uncertain outcomes and potential harm to physical, social, or psychological well-being (McCormack & Wignall, 2017). Among young adults, this includes substance use, unsafe sex, reckless driving, and violence exposure (Kipping et al., 2012). Persistent engagement in such behaviors undermines health and psychosocial functioning (Babor et al., 2007) and is associated with significant morbidity and mortality (Bozzini et al., 2021; Guilamo-Ramos et al., 2005). Individuals with childhood abuse are particularly susceptible to chronic risky behavioral patterns (Hockenberry et al., 2010; Van et al., 2018).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Attachment Theory: Attachment theory describes the emotional bond between children and caregivers and its role in shaping emotional regulation, relational security, and psychological

development (Bowlby, 1969; Ainsworth et al., 1978). Childhood trauma often disrupts attachment patterns, contributing to long-term emotional dysregulation and difficulties forming secure relationships (Erozkan, 2016; Lahousen et al., 2019). The present study integrates attachment theory to explain how early trauma influences later resilience, and risk-taking behavior.

Psychoanalytical Theory: Psychoanalytic perspectives propose that trauma results from repressed memories and emotions that later manifest as psychological symptoms such as anxiety, depression, or PTSD (Bohleber, 2007). According to this view, unresolved traumatic experiences resurface through maladaptive coping patterns, including risk taking behaviours.

Resilience Theory: Rutter's resilience theory emphasizes that positive outcomes can emerge despite serious adversity and that resilience reflects an interaction between risk exposure and protective resources (Rutter & Michael et al., 2012). He argues that resilience is not an inherent trait but arises when individuals are provided adequate environmental support. Children raised in neglectful or harmful environments are 76% more likely to develop risky behaviors, demonstrating the cumulative effect of adversity on later outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A correlational research design was used to investigate the relationships among study variables. Relevant statistical procedures were applied to determine the nature and strength of the associations.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING STRATEGY

Purposive sampling was used to collect data from the target population. This non-probability sampling method selects participants based on specific characteristics required for the study (Campbell et al., 2020). The sample consisted of (N = 210) university students aged 18–25 years, including (N = 64) males and (N = 146) females with M (1.30) and S.D (0.46).

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

- Individuals aged 18–25 years
- Individuals engaged in risky behaviours during the past six months

- Individuals with a history of childhood trauma

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Transgender, disables, and individuals with psychological illness

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Childhood Emotional Abuse: Childhood emotional abuse, also known as psychological abuse, is the persistent emotional mistreatment of a child that conveys they are worthless, unloved, or only valued for meeting someone else's needs (Bernstein et al., 2003).

Resilience: Resilience describes how quickly individuals recover from adversity, cope with difficult situations, and return to normal functioning (Smith et al., 2008).

Risky Behaviors: Risky behavior involves decision-making under uncertainty, influenced by individual differences in risk attitude, explained through expected utility theory and prospect theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Blais & Weber, 2006).

ASSESSMENT MEASURES

Informed Consent Form: Participants were informed about the study purpose and assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Participation was voluntary, and withdrawal at any time carried no consequences.

Demographic Information Sheet: Basic and specific participant information was collected, including age, gender, education, university, semester, siblings, area of residence, family income, family structure, history of abuse and risky behaviours, religion.

CHILDHOOD TRAUMA QUESTIONNAIRE (CTQ-SF)

The subscale of emotional abuse score from childhood trauma questionnaire was used to assess the childhood emotional abuse containing 5-point Likert scale (Bernstein et al., 2003).

Brief Resilience Scale (BRS): The BRS evaluates perceived ability to recover from stress, with scores ranging from 1 (low resilience) to 5 (high resilience). Reported reliability is .91 (Smith et al., 2008).

Domain Specific Risk Taking (DOSPERT) Scale:

For this study, 11 items were selected from the DOSPERT scale—six assessing health/safety risk and five assessing social risk. Items are rated on a Likert scale from 1 to 7. Reliability ranges from $\alpha = 0.70$ to 0.87 .

Stimulating and Instrumental Risk Scale (S & IRQ): This 8-item scale measures stimulating and instrumental risk-taking tendencies (Makarowski, 2013). Internal consistency values range from 0.69 to 0.83 .

PROCEDURE

Study objectives were finalized, and permission for relevant scales was obtained from the authors. A literature review, including indigenous and international research, was completed.

Participants meeting the inclusion criteria were approached in universities. Written informed consent was obtained, and anonymity and confidentiality were assured. Participants completed the demographic sheet and questionnaires after receiving instructions. Each participant took approximately 10–15 minutes to complete the survey. Data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation and relevant statistical procedures to test the hypotheses.

Table 1. Psychometric Properties of Scales and Subscales (N=210)

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Authors' permission for scale use was obtained. The study purpose and nature were explained to all participants. Participation was voluntary with the right to withdraw. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained. APA 7 citation and referencing guidelines were followed. No plagiarism or unethical practices were involved.

RESULTS

The main focus of this study was to link these variable including childhood emotional abuse, resilience, and risky behavior and find the predictive role of emotional abuse and resilience on risky behaviors. SPSS version 25 was utilized for analysis purposes. Screening of the data was carried out initially to check if there were any missing values and to find any possible outliers within the data. Afterward, descriptive statistics were executed from demographic variables.

Scales	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Ranges</i>	Cronbach's α
EA	15.32	6.07	5-25	.89
BRS	17.12	3.69	8-25	.83
TDOSPERT	43.01	12.74	11-68	.87
DOSHS	20.53	8.97	6-40	.85
DOSS	22.49	6.15	5-33	.81
TSIRQ	16.77	4.99	8-40	.71
SR	7.73	3.17	4-20	.75
IR	9.05	3.24	4-20	.66

Table 1 Note. M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, α =Cronbach Alpha, EA= Emotional Abuse, BRS= Brief, Resilience Scale, DOSHS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale Health/safety, DOSS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking scale social
 The above table 1 shows descriptive statistics and the reliability coefficient of the scales and subscales used in the present study.

The Emotional Abuse scale demonstrated a mean score of 15.32 (SD = 6.07), with observed scores ranging from 5 to 25. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .89, indicating excellent internal

consistency. This suggests that the items on the EA scale reliably assess participants' experiences of childhood emotional maltreatment. The BRS showed a mean of 17.12 (SD = 3.69), with scores ranging from 8 to 25. The reliability coefficient of .83 reflects strong internal consistency, indicating that the scale provides a stable and coherent measure of resilience across individuals. The total risk-taking score (combining all DOSPERT domains) had a mean of 43.01 (SD = 12.74), with a broad observed range of 11 to 68. The Cronbach's alpha of .87 demonstrates high

reliability, suggesting that the composite risk-taking measure effectively captures consistent patterns of risk-related behaviour. The DOSHS subscale displayed a mean of 20.53 (SD = 8.97) and scores ranging from 6 to 40. The Cronbach's alpha value of .85 indicates strong reliability, supporting the coherence of items assessing health- and safety-

related risk-taking tendencies. The DOSS subscale had a mean score of 22.49 (SD = 6.15), with observed scores between 5 and 33. The reliability coefficient of .81 reflects good internal consistency, confirming that the items in this domain consistently measure socially oriented risk-taking behaviours.

Table 2. Correlation between Childhood Emotional Abuse, Resilience, and Risky Behavior.

Variable	Childhood Emotional Abuse	Resilience	DOSHS	DOSS
Childhood Emotional Abuse	1	-.31***	.22*	.37***
BRS	-		-.13*	-.15*
DOSHS	-	-	1	.50***
DOSS	-	-	-	1

Table 2 Note. DOSHS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale Health/safety, DOSS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking scale social. *= $p < .05$, **= $p < .01$, ***= $p < .001$.

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted using to examine the strength and direction of relationships among childhood emotional abuse, resilience and two domains of risk-taking behaviour: health/safety (DOSHS) and social risk-taking (DOSS). The correlation coefficients provide insight into how emotional abuse influences risk-related outcomes and the extent to which resilience interacts with these variables. Emotional abuse showed significant positive correlations with the DOSHS (health/safety risk-taking): $r = .22$, $p < .05$. This correlation indicates that higher levels of emotional abuse are associated with greater engagement in health- and safety-related risky behaviours (e.g., reckless actions, substance-related risks). Emotional abuse and DOSS (social risk-taking) also showed positive relationship $r = .37$, $P < .001$. Emotional abuse and resilience ($r = -.31$, $p < .001$) significant negative correlation which indicated that individuals

exposed to higher levels of emotional abuse tend to report lower resilience. Emotional abuse may diminish adaptive coping abilities and emotional strength, which in turn heightens susceptibility to risk-taking behaviours. Resilience and DOSHS (health/safety risk-taking): ($r = -.13$, $p < .05$) exhibited significant negative correlation suggests that higher resilience is associated with lower engagement in health/safety risky behaviours. Resilient individuals may possess stronger regulatory skills and healthier coping mechanisms, making them less likely to engage in dangerous or impulsive behaviours. Resilience and DOSS (social risk-taking): ($r = -.15$, $p < .05$). showed negative association indicates that resilience also contributes to reduced social risk-taking, possibly through improved decision-making and emotional stability. DOSHS and DOSS ($r = .50$, $p < .001$). showed strong positive correlation between both risk-taking domains suggests that individuals who take high risks in one area (e.g., health/safety) are likely to do so in another (e.g., social situations). This reflects a broader tendency toward risk-prone behavioural patterns.

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Predicting Risky Behaviour (N=210)

Variable	Risky Behaviors Health/Safety				Risky Behaviors Social							
	β	95% CI for B		SE B	β	R ²	β	95% CI for B		SE B	β	R ²
		LL	UL					LL	UL			
						.52						.46
Constant	5.5	-6.5	17.4	6.1			11.4	2.9	19.9	4.3		
CEA	-.41***	-.65	-.17	.113	-.28***		.21**	.03	.38	.09	.20**	
Resilience	.26*	-.017	.535	.140	.16*		.19*	-.01	.39	.11	.12*	

Note. SE=Standard error, β = Beta, CI= Coefficient interval, R² =R Square, CEA= Childhood Emotional Abuse * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 3 showed the multiple linear regression analyses were conducted to examine the predictive role of childhood emotional abuse and resilience on domains of risky behaviour including health/safety risk-taking and social risk-taking. Standardized beta coefficients, confidence intervals, and R² values were used to evaluate the significance and strength of these predictors. The regression model for health and safety-related risky behaviours accounted for a substantial proportion of variance (R² = .52). Emotional abuse emerged as a significant predictor ($\beta = -.41$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher levels of emotional abuse were associated with lower engagement in health/safety risky behaviours. This negative association may reflect a tendency among

emotionally abused individuals to internalize distress rather than engage in overt, externally directed risks. Resilience also significantly predicts health/safety risk-taking ($\beta = .26$), suggesting that adaptive coping abilities substantially shape risk-taking tendencies in this behavioural domain. The model predicting social risky behaviours explained 46% of the variance (R² = .46). Emotional abuse was a significant positive predictor ($\beta = -.21$, $p < .01$), indicating that individuals with higher emotional abuse scores demonstrated greater engagement in socially oriented risk-taking, such as socially daring or interpersonal challenges. Resilience also significantly predicted social risk-taking ($\beta = .19$), although the trend indicated that higher resilience may be associated with greater willingness to engage in socially expressive risks.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test Comparing Study Variables in Men and Women in terms of childhood emotional abuse, resilience and risky behavior (N=210)

Variable	Women		Men		t (df)	P	95% CI		Cohen's d
	(n = 146)		(n = 64)				LL	UL	
	M	SD	M	SD					
EA	14.9	6.1	16.3	5.9	-1.6(208)	.13	-3.18	.39	0.23
BR	18.5	5.9	22.3	4.7	-4.7(208)	.000	-5.5	-2.3	0.72
DOSHS	19.5	9.1	22.9	8.4	-2.6(208)	.010	-6.1	-.82	0.39
DOSS	21.8	6.9	24.3	2.9	-3.8(207.5)	.000	-3.9	-1.3	0.48

Note: CEA= Childhood Emotional Abuse, BRS= Brief Resilience, DOSHS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking scale Health/safety, DOSS= Domain-Specific Risk-Taking scale social, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

An Independent sample t-test was carried out and the results showed that there were no significant gender differences in the childhood

emotional with mean higher in male ($M=16.3$, $SD=5.9$) than female ($M=14.9$, $SD=6.1$). A significant gender difference was found for resilience. Men ($M = 22.3$, $SD = 4.7$) scored significantly higher than women ($M = 18.5$, $SD = 5.9$), $t(208) = -4.7$, $p < .001$. The confidence interval (-5.5 to -2.3) did not include zero, indicating a robust difference. The effect size was large (Cohen's $d = 0.72$), demonstrating that men in this sample exhibited substantially higher resilience compared to women. This finding indicates stronger perceived coping abilities and adaptive functioning among male participants. Men ($M = 22.9$, $SD = 8.4$) reported significantly higher engagement in health/safety risky behaviours than women ($M = 19.5$, $SD = 9.1$), $t(208) = -2.6$, $p = .01$. The confidence interval (-6.1 to -0.82) confirmed the significance of this difference. The effect size was moderate (Cohen's $d = 0.39$), suggesting that males are somewhat more likely to engage in physically hazardous or impulsive actions such as reckless behaviour or safety-related risks. Significant gender differences were also observed for social risky behaviours. Men ($M = 24.3$, $SD = 2.9$) scored higher than women ($M = 21.8$, $SD = 6.9$), $t(207.5) = -3.8$, $p < .001$, with the confidence interval (-3.9 to -1.3) indicating a clear difference. The effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.48$) was moderate, suggesting that males are more inclined toward socially oriented risk-taking behaviours, such as socially bold actions or reputation-challenging activities.

DISCUSSION

The primary objective of this study was to examine the interrelationships and predictive effects of childhood emotional abuse, resilience, and risky behaviour among young adults. The findings are consistent with existing theoretical and empirical literature demonstrating the long-term behavioural consequences of early emotional adversity.

The correlational analysis provided clear support for the enduring negative consequences of childhood abuse. Consistent with prior research (e.g., Edinger et al., 2020; Gopalan, 2022), found a positive and statistically significant association between childhood emotional abuse and risky behavior. This implies that greater exposure to early traumatic experiences, such as emotional abuse significantly increases the likelihood of engaging in externalized risky behaviors later in life. This positive association between childhood abuse

and risky behavior was further validated by the multiple linear regression analysis and is consistent with literature citing increased substance use, sexual risk-taking, and aggressive behaviors among trauma survivors (He et al., 2022; Sharmin et al., 2020). Abuse-exposed individuals may exhibit heightened risk-taking due to poor emotional regulation, impulsivity, or a lack of future-oriented thinking, often as a means of coping or dissociation (Sontate et al., 2021).¹

As hypothesized, analysis also revealed a statistically significant negative relationship between childhood emotional abuse and resilience. This suggests that childhood abuse compromises an individual's ability to develop robust adaptive resources, increasing their vulnerability to maladaptive behaviors, a finding consistent with other research (Nishimi et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021)

However, the regression analysis indicated that resilience was a positive significant predictor for risky behavior. This finding is counterintuitive. It suggests that, within this specific young adult population, individuals who score higher on resilience are more likely to engage in certain health, safety, and social risks. One possible explanation could be that resilience is being expressed as perceived invulnerability or optimism, leading to an overestimation of one's ability to cope with negative outcomes and thus encouraging risk-taking. This highlights the nuanced relationship between resilience and specific behavioral outcomes.

emotional abuse were found to be negative predictors of risk-taking behavior. The interpretation offered—that abused individuals might lose their "charm" or motivation to engage in any risk, even necessary ones—is a compelling clinical insight but needs more qualitative or longitudinal research to fully validate. It suggests that specific forms of trauma (neglect/abuse) might lead to behavioral withdrawal rather than externalized risk-taking.

In line with the next hypothesis and consistent with previous literature (Arnett, 2014; Bahramnejad et al., 2021), the independent samples t-test revealed statistically significant gender differences across all major variables. The mean scores for childhood emotional abuse, resilience, and risky behavior were all higher in males than in females.

This pattern suggests that, within this university sample, male students reported higher rates of

exposure to childhood abuse, demonstrated lower resilience, and exhibited greater engagement in risky behaviors compared to their female counterparts. This contrasts with some literature suggesting higher resilience in women (Infurna et al., 2011). These findings underscore the need for gender-sensitive intervention strategies, recognizing that male students may internalize and externalize the effects of trauma in ways that put them at higher risk for severe outcomes, including self-harm and risky social engagement (Li et al., 2020; Wiggers & Paas, 2022).

Implications

The findings of this study carry important implications for clinical practice, public health, and research:

Preventative Focus on Risky Behavior: The significant association between childhood abuse and risky behaviors underscores the importance of early intervention programs aimed at developing alternative coping mechanisms to reduce the likelihood of high-risk engagement (e.g., substance use, unsafe sexual practices).

Resilience Reframing: The negative correlation between trauma and resilience highlights the need for resilience-focused therapies to mitigate the long-lasting negative impact of childhood trauma on mental health. Programs should focus on teaching effective emotion regulation and problem-solving skills.

Gender-Specific Interventions: The finding that males reported higher scores across abuse and risky behavior suggests an urgent need to develop gender-tailored therapeutic approaches that address the unique ways male young adults process and externalize distress resulting from trauma.

LIMITATIONS

Sample Size and Generalizability: The relatively small and non-diverse sample size limits the statistical power and the generalizability of the findings, particularly to young adults outside the university setting or from different geographical regions.

Cross-Sectional Design: The study utilized a cross-sectional design, which captures data at a single point in time. This prevents the establishment of a definitive causal relationship between the variables (e.g., proving trauma causes self-mutilation) or tracking the development of resilience over time.

Methodological Constraints: Relying solely on quantitative methods (self-report measures) may not capture the full complexity, nuance, and subjective experience of the participants, especially concerning sensitive topics like trauma and self-mutilation.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Longitudinal Studies: Future research should employ longitudinal designs to better understand the temporal and causal ordering of the relationships between childhood emotional, resilience development, and the onset of maladaptive behaviors.

Larger and Diverse Samples: Conducting studies with a larger, more diverse sample across multiple institutions and geographical locations will enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Mixed-Methods Approach: Integrating qualitative methods (e.g., in-depth interviews) would provide richer, more contextualized data to explore the mechanisms underlying the relationships, such as how emotional neglect specifically impacts risk-taking motivation.

CONCLUSION

The study sought to investigate the association between childhood emotional abuse, resilience, and risky behaviour among Pakistani university students. A purposive sampling technique was used to acquire a sample of $N = 210$ young adults between the ages of 18 and 25, with 146 women and 64 men. Data analysis showed a significant and positive correlation between Childhood emotional abuse. Risk-taking (health and safety) showed a negative correlation with childhood emotional abuse while risk-taking social decisions showed a positive significant correlation with childhood emotional abuse. A significant gender difference was found with men being higher in the ratio of involvement in risk-taking behaviour. These findings highlight the important factors of involvement of young adults in risky behaviour since the dawn of the increasing numbers of cases but yet these cases are being neglected in Pakistan. With the help of these findings, a mental health professional trained in evidence-based trauma treatment can help adults cope with the impact of trauma and move toward recovery, act of risk-taking behaviour can be managed in more

interventional ways since emotional abuse has been neglected issue in Pakistan

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